

Prevention of Postoperative Penile Erection and Pain Following Penile Surgeries: A Hospital Based Retrospective Study

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Abstract:

Background: Painful erections are a postoperative complication of penile and urethral reconstructive surgeries. **Objectives:** The primary objective of the present study was to evaluate the efficacy of Ketoconazole to inhibit painful postoperative erections after penile and urethral reconstructive surgery. The secondary objectives were to evaluate the incidence of side effects with Ketoconazole including variations in liver function tests.

Methods: This was a hospital based retrospective study conducted in the Department of General Surgery, tertiary healthcare facility in South India between January and June 2024 among males more than or equal to 16 years of age (up to 60 years of age) with phimosis or balanoposthitis who had undergone penile or urethral surgery.

Results: The baseline characteristics of our study groups, including age and type of surgery, did not show significant differences. The results showed that the difference in incidence of erections and painful erections between the study groups was found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). It was found that the study groups did not vary significantly ($p > 0.05$) by incidence of nausea/vomiting and liver function test results. Also, the lower mean (SD) VAS scores observed in the study group at all measured timepoints (24 hours, 48 hours, 72 hours, and 1 week postoperatively), in comparison with the control group were statistically significant at all timepoints ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: Ketoconazole is effective in significantly reducing the incidence of postoperative erections and the associated pain following penile and urethral reconstructive surgery. However, the findings underscore the importance of monitoring for adverse effects, particularly hepatotoxicity, to ensure patient safety.

Keywords: Postoperative penile erection, pain, Penile surgery, Urethral surgery.

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Introduction

Penile and urethral reconstructive surgeries are commonly performed to address various conditions such as phimosis, balanoposthitis, and urethral strictures.[1, 2] These surgeries, while essential for correcting anatomical and functional issues, often lead to postoperative complications, one of which is the occurrence of painful erections.[3]

Postoperative erections can cause significant discomfort, impede healing, and potentially result in complications such as wound dehiscence or suture disruption.[4] Managing these erections effectively is crucial for improving patient outcomes and postoperative recovery. Postoperative erections, whether nocturnal or

spontaneous, can be particularly distressing for patients recovering from penile or urethral surgeries.[5] The physiological mechanism behind these erections involves increased blood flow and engorgement of the penile tissue, which, following surgery, can exacerbate pain and discomfort.[6] This pain is often severe enough to necessitate the use of analgesics, which themselves can have undesirable side effects.

Pain management in the context of postoperative erections is challenging due to the need for medications that can both inhibit erections and manage pain without causing significant side effects.[7] Traditional pain management strategies

may not adequately address the underlying issue of frequent erections, necessitating the exploration of alternative pharmacological options. Ketoconazole, an antifungal agent, has been explored for its off-label use in managing conditions associated with unwanted erections. Ketoconazole exerts its effects by inhibiting steroidogenesis, particularly the synthesis of testosterone, through the blockade of cytochrome P450 enzymes in the adrenal glands and gonads.[8] By reducing testosterone levels, Ketoconazole can diminish the frequency and intensity of erections, providing a dual benefit of pain relief and decreased mechanical stress on surgical sites.[9] The efficacy of Ketoconazole in managing priapism,[10] a condition characterized by prolonged and painful erections, has been documented in several studies.[11-13] However, the use of Ketoconazole is not without risks; it is known to cause side effects such as nausea, vomiting, and hepatotoxicity, necessitating careful monitoring of liver function tests.[14]

Against this background, the primary objective of the present study was to evaluate the efficacy of Ketoconazole to inhibit painful postoperative erections after penile and urethral reconstructive surgery. The secondary objectives were to evaluate the incidence of side effects with Ketoconazole including variations in liver function tests.

Materials and Methods

This was a hospital based retrospective study conducted in the inpatient wards of the Department of General Surgery, tertiary healthcare facility in South India between January and June 2024. The study was approved by the Institutional Human Ethics Committee (IHEC). After obtaining necessary approvals from the Dean, Medical Superintendent, and the Head of Medical records department (MRD), the electronic medical records and laboratory information system were accessed (including surgical logs, clinical records and ambulatory surgery notes).

All the patients who had undergone penile or urethral surgery in the past year (January to December 2023) in the Department of General Surgery were enrolled, provided they were males more than or equal to 16 years of age (up to 60 years of age) with phimosis or balanoposthitis. Patients who had been prescribed Ketoconazole in the immediate postoperative period were designated the study group; and the patients who did not receive ketoconazole were designated the control group. We excluded patients on medications for erectile dysfunction including antidepressants, statins, antihistamines, diuretics and hypertensive medications.

The outcome of interest (erections in the postoperative period) was noted as, patients experiencing or not experiencing erections during

the immediate postoperative period (designated as the first 2 weeks after the operation, or the length of time during which the patient took ketoconazole). Patients experiencing nocturnal, spontaneous, or diminished erections and/or erections caused by stimulation were categorized as experiencing erections. Patients experiencing erections that were painful enough to cause them to take, or want to take, pain medication were further categorized as experiencing painful erections. To quantify the intensity of pain, we used visual analogue scale (VAS) scores (scores ranging between 0 and 10).[15]

The data obtained was manually entered into Microsoft Excel and analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) v23. All the categorical variables were summarised using frequencies and percentages. Continuous variables were summarized using mean (standard deviation) and/or median (interquartile range) (based on the results of data normality, tested using Kolmogorov–Smirnov test and the Shapiro–Wilk test). To test for statistical significance, Chi square test or Fisher exact test (for categorical variables) and independent “t” test or Mann Whitney U test (for continuous variables) was used. Statistical significance was considered at p value less than 0.05.

Results

We retrieved data of a total of 111 patients who had undergone penile or urethral surgery in the past year. However, after excluding patients with incomplete records we included a total of 100 patients – 50 patients who had received Ketoconazole in the immediate postoperative period (Study group or Group A); and 50 patients who did not receive ketoconazole (Control group or Group B).

Baseline characteristics of the study groups: The mean (SD) age of the study group was 29.3 years (7.3), and that of the control group was 28.2 years (9.1). More than half the patients in the study group (58.0%) were less than 30 years of age; and similarly, more than half the patients in the control group (54.0%) were less than 30 years of age. Importantly, the study groups did not vary significantly by age ($p > 0.05$). Of the 50 patients in the study group, 58.0% had urethroplasty, 36.0% had circumcision, and 8.0% had other surgeries including meatoplasty. Similarly, of the 50 patients in the control group, 22 patients (44.0%) had urethroplasty, 19 patients (38.0%) had circumcision, and 9 patients (18.0%) had other surgeries including meatoplasty. The test of association showed that the study groups did not vary significantly by the type of surgery ($p > 0.05$).

Comparison of study groups by outcomes of interest: The results showed that 22.0% patients in

the study group had erections whereas, nearly three fourth patients (70.0%) in the control group had erections – the difference in incidence of erections between the study groups was found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). In terms of painful erections, 8 patients (16.0%) in the study group had painful erections and nearly three fourth patients (70.0%) in the control group had painful erections – the difference in incidence of painful erections between the study groups was found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

The results showed that 10.0% patients in the study group and 2.0% patients in the control group had nausea and/or vomiting; 2.0% patients in the study group and none of the patients in the control group (0.0%) had increased liver function tests.

Importantly, the results signify that the study groups did not vary significantly ($p > 0.05$) by incidence of nausea/vomiting and liver function test results.

The mean (SD) visual analogue scale (VAS) scores at 24 hours in the study group was 8.8 (0.7) and in the control group was 9.7 (0.9); at 48 hours in the study group was 6.4 (0.4) and in the control group was 6.9 (0.5); at 72 hours in the study group was 4.9 (0.7) and in the control group was 5.4 (0.3); at 1 week in the study group was 3.1 (0.6) and in the control group was 3.4 (0.7). The lower VAS scores observed in the study group, in comparison with the control group were statistically significant at all timepoints ($p < 0.05$).

Table 1: Baseline characteristics of the study participants

		Study group (N = 50) n (%)	Control group (N = 50) n (%)	P value
Age (in years) Mean (SD)		29.3 (7.3)	28.2 (9.1)	0.507
Age (in years)	Less than 30	29 (58.0)	27 (54.0)	0.687
	>30	21 (42.0)	23 (46.0)	
Type of surgery	Urethroplasty	29 (58.0)	22 (44.0)	0.136
	Circumcision	18 (36.0)	19 (38.0)	
	Others [#]	3 (6.0)	9 (18.0)	

[#]Others included Meatoplasty, SD, Standard deviation, *Statistically significant at $p < 0.05$

Table 2: Comparison of study groups by outcomes of interest

		Study group (N = 50) n (%)	Control group (N = 50) n (%)	P value
Erections	Present	11 (22.0)	35 (70.0)	<0.001*
	Absent	39 (78.0)	15 (30.0)	
Painful erections	Present	8 (16.0)	35 (70.0)	<0.001*
	Absent	42 (84.0)	15 (30.0)	
Nausea/Vomiting	Present	5 (10.0)	1 (2.0)	0.092
	Absent	45 (90.0)	49 (98.0)	
LFT	Increased	1 (2.0)	0 (0.0)	0.988
	Normal	49 (98.0)	50 (100)	

LFT, Liver function tests, *Statistically significant at $p < 0.05$

Discussion

The aim of our study was to evaluate the efficacy of Ketoconazole in inhibiting painful postoperative erections after penile and urethral reconstructive surgery. The baseline characteristics of our study groups, including age and type of surgery, did not show significant differences, indicating that the groups were comparable. This strengthens the validity of our findings by reducing confounding variables that could influence the incidence of postoperative erections and their associated pain. Our results demonstrated a significant reduction in the incidence of erections among patients who received Ketoconazole (22.0%) compared to those who did not (70.0%). This indicates that Ketoconazole is effective in reducing the occurrence of postoperative erections, which is

consistent with the findings of previous studies that have shown Ketoconazole's ability to reduce androgen levels, thus diminishing erectile responses.[16] Our study also found that the incidence of painful erections was significantly lower in the Ketoconazole group (16.0%) compared to the control group (70.0%). This significant reduction in painful erections among patients administered Ketoconazole aligns with its known pharmacological effects of suppressing testosterone synthesis,[17] which is critical in reducing the frequency and intensity of spontaneous erections. The use of Ketoconazole to manage postoperative erections is further supported by its success in treating other conditions characterized by unwanted erections, such as priapism.[13]

Figure 1: Comparison of study groups by outcomes of interest

Table 3: Comparison of study groups by visual analogue scale (VAS) scores

		Study group	Control group	P value
		N = 50	N = 50	
		Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	
VAS scores	At 24 hours	8.8 (0.7)	9.7 (0.9)	<0.001*
	At 48 hours	6.4 (0.4)	6.9 (0.5)	<0.001*
	At 72 hours	4.9 (0.7)	5.4 (0.3)	0.001*
	At 1 week	3.1 (0.6)	3.4 (0.7)	0.041*

VAS, Visual analogue scale; SD, Standard deviation, *Statistically significant at p<0.05

Figure 2: Comparison of study groups by visual analogue scale (VAS) scores

The Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) scores showed that patients in the Ketoconazole group experienced significantly less pain at all measured timepoints (24 hours, 48 hours, 72 hours, and 1 week postoperatively) compared to the control group. This suggests that Ketoconazole not only reduces the frequency of postoperative erections but also alleviates the associated pain. These results align with previous studies that have highlighted the analgesic effects of Ketoconazole in similar contexts.[18] The reduction in pain scores over time further supports the efficacy of Ketoconazole in improving postoperative comfort and potentially enhancing recovery. Our secondary objectives included assessing the incidence of side effects associated with Ketoconazole. We found that 10.0% of patients in the study group experienced nausea and/or vomiting, compared to 2.0% in the control group. Additionally, 2.0% of patients in the study group showed increased liver function tests, whereas none in the control group did. Although these differences were not statistically significant, they underscore the importance of monitoring for potential adverse effects. Nausea and vomiting are known side effects of Ketoconazole, which have been reported in previous studies.[14] While the incidence was higher in the Ketoconazole group, it remained within acceptable limits. The observed hepatotoxicity, although not statistically significant, is a well-documented risk associated with Ketoconazole. Routine liver function monitoring is therefore crucial for patients receiving this medication, to detect and manage potential hepatotoxicity early.[19]

The significant reduction in both the incidence of erections and pain intensity in the Ketoconazole group highlights its potential as a therapeutic agent for managing postoperative complications in penile and urethral surgeries. By reducing the frequency of painful erections, Ketoconazole can improve patient comfort and potentially expedite recovery. However, the potential side effects, particularly hepatotoxicity, necessitate careful patient selection and monitoring.[20] Despite the promising findings, our study has several limitations. The retrospective design limits control over confounding factors, and the sample size, although adequate, could be expanded in future studies to enhance the robustness and generalizability of the findings. Additionally, reliance on self-reported pain scores and clinical records introduces potential bias and inaccuracies.

Future research should focus on prospective, randomized controlled trials to validate these findings and explore the long-term safety and efficacy of Ketoconazole in this context. Investigations into optimal dosing regimens and alternative administration routes could also help minimize side effects while maintaining efficacy.

Additionally, exploring patient-reported outcomes and quality of life measures would provide a more comprehensive understanding of Ketoconazole's impact on postoperative recovery.

Conclusion

The present study demonstrates that Ketoconazole is effective in significantly reducing the incidence of postoperative erections and the associated pain following penile and urethral reconstructive surgery. Patients who received Ketoconazole experienced fewer and less painful erections compared to those who did not, as evidenced by lower VAS scores at all postoperative time points measured. While Ketoconazole was associated with a higher incidence of nausea and vomiting and showed a potential risk for increased liver function tests, these side effects were not statistically significant. These findings underscore the importance of monitoring for adverse effects, particularly hepatotoxicity, to ensure patient safety. Overall, Ketoconazole appears to be a valuable therapeutic option for managing postoperative erections and improving patient comfort. Future studies should focus on prospective, randomized controlled trials to confirm these findings and further evaluate the long-term safety and efficacy of Ketoconazole in this patient population. With careful patient selection and monitoring, Ketoconazole can be effectively integrated into postoperative care protocols for penile and urethral reconstructive surgeries.

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